

Welcome to the Carpentries Community

We are happy that you are here! [The Carpentries](#) is an organisation that teaches researchers foundational coding and data science skills worldwide using open-source software. It relies on volunteer contributions to support the [community of practice](#) whose members share [our core values](#). This document highlights key links and activities to help you get started in the Carpentries community.

Where Do I Get Started?

I'm glad you asked! Here are a few things we recommend to everyone:

- **[Review the Code of Conduct](#)**: We are dedicated to providing a welcoming and supportive environment for all people. You agree to abide by our Code of Conduct by participating in this community.
- **[Shared values and goals](#)** have long been the starting point for communities of practice, as they identify the changes they want to see and work together towards them.
- **[Attend a Welcome Session!](#)** Join members of the Core Team and the community to learn about the organisation and ways to engage, and have your questions answered.

How Do I Get Connected?

The Carpentries offers many options for connecting, collaborating and networking within the community. Worried about too many communications? Don't be! Only subscribe to the communications you want, and you can unsubscribe anytime.

- **The Carpentries Slack** ([Join Link](#)) ([Slack Quickstart Guide](#))
- **Email Mailing Lists** ([Mailing List Directory](#))
- **Monthly Newsletter - The Carpentries Clippings** ([Subscribe](#))
- **Blog** ([Posts](#))
- **Social media**: Follow our organisation's activities on
 - [Mastodon](#), [BlueSky](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#).

How Do I Get Involved?

Whether you have a little or a lot of time, there are many ways to contribute and engage with us.

- **Community Events**: Topics range from teaching workshops and developing curricula to building local communities and assessing the global impact of our workshops. Our community calendar lists all The Carpentries' activities.
 - **[Community Sessions](#)**: There are many opportunities to join community meetings, subcommittees and debriefing sessions. Sign up for Community sessions on [Pretix](#), subscribe to the Google calendar below, or use this [ICS feed](#) to stay up to date on what's going on throughout our community.
 - **[Regional Communities Mailing Lists](#)**: All [mailing lists for The Carpentries](#) are hosted on Topicbox. This includes several mailing lists specific to local or regional communities.

- [Subcommunity register](#): A subcommunity brings together a subset of the larger Carpentries community, which can be local, regional, domain-specific, or a group of community members sharing a common language or interests. We invite you to browse the subcommunities in this registry to identify ones you might be interested in joining.
- **Volunteering**: If you are still determining how you would like to engage, our [Get Involved page](#) on our website lists options and opportunities.

If you are already involved in The Carpentries community, you may find other Tip Sheets or Quick Start Guides helpful:

- [Instructor Tip Sheet](#)
- [TopicBox Quickstart Guide](#)
- [Mastodon Quickstart Guide](#)

Additional Resources

- [Carpentries.org](#): The official website of The Carpentries organisation.
- [Handbook](#): A go-to resource (or support documentation) for all things Carpentries.
- [Our Community Glossary](#): Glossary that defines common terms used in The Carpentries community

Questions

If you have questions, please email our Core Team. We are here to help you begin your journey with our organisation. Welcome!

Citation and Re-use

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